

Milovanovitch, M. (2022). System change for lifelong learning: Cross-country digest of policies for lifelong learning in countries of the European neighbourhood. In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 100–111). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6977034>

System Change for Lifelong learning: Cross-Country Digest of Policies for Lifelong Learning in Countries of the European Neighbourhood

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Abstract

Context: Since 2010, the European Training Foundation – an EU Agency – is partnering with countries in South-East Europe, Central Asia, the Eastern Partnership region, South and East Mediterranean and Turkey for regular biannual reviews of developments in the field of vocational education and training. The latest round in 2018-2021 shows that in all countries, education and training systems are under pressure to find ways to meet the learning demand of a growing number of people – youth and adults - who see their career choices and life prospects challenged by recent developments, such as the COVID19 pandemic. In this context, lifelong learning is seeing a certain resurgence as a priority in the policy and reform discourse of national authorities in these countries. The purpose of our work was to explore whether the creation of lifelong learning opportunities is a priority in the reform agenda of these countries in education and training and if yes, we wanted to investigate the ways in which lifelong learning is influencing reforms in particular in vocational education and training (IVET and CVET).

Approach: Our research is based on an inductive thematic analysis of a total of 26 national reports, 22 bilateral interviews with partner country representatives, and a focus group with international partners. These three sources were compiled into a repository covering the immediate pre-pandemic period (2018-2020), the phase of initial lockdown and provider closures in 2020, and the time of emerging reopening and post-pandemic debate in 2020-2021. We then carried out inductive thematic analysis which returned 5 000 segments of evidence that were deemed relevant for their explanatory power regarding the research questions.

Findings and conclusions: Our findings show that at present, the creation and promotion of opportunities for LLL is gaining in importance, but also that it is still an underdeveloped policy area: the narratives of countries are often dominated by referrals to decades-old legacy systems of adult education and to preservation instead of change and where they refer to LLL in a more forward-looking manner, they do so by declaring LLL as the broader goal of policy reforms, without a clear association with policy implementation actions. Although the countries in our sample do not yet operationalize LLL as a stand-alone area of planning and action, they do devote time and resources to other areas which are essential as the elements of building blocks of a lifelong learning system, such as recognition of prior learning or individualised support for learners. The selection of elements in focus of reform is still quite limited and they are not necessarily well-connected and coordinated yet. This fits into a broader pattern of fragmentation of LLL as a policy domain, which may prevent the planning and coordination of actions and the division of responsibilities. Addressing this fragmentation could be an important step towards promoting LLL as a practical and not only strategic policy solution.

Keywords: lifelong learning, policy reform, COVID19, EU neighbourhood

1 Introduction

1.1 Research Focus

This chapter summarises the findings of a cross-country research¹ by the European Training Foundation (ETF) of policies and actions in support of lifelong learning in 26 countries in South-East Europe, Central Asia, the Eastern Partnership region, South and East Mediterranean and Turkey. A full list of countries covered in the research can be found in Table 1 below.

The purpose of our work was to explore whether the creation of lifelong learning opportunities is a priority in the reform agenda of these countries in education and training and if yes, we wanted to investigate the ways in which lifelong learning is influencing reforms in particular in vocational education and training (IVET and CVET).

We were also interested in the efforts of national authorities and local stakeholders to implement their reform plans in the wake of changing circumstances before and during the COVID19 pandemic, as well as in the policy gaps and lessons to be learned in a cross-country perspective.

1.2 Sources of Evidence

For the preparation of this contribution, we relied on primary evidence from several sources. The first sources were national reports prepared by ETF partner countries in the course of the most recent round (2018-2020) of the Torino Process: a biennial, country-led review of VET in the partner regions listed above. These reports capture the results of structured self-reporting by national authorities and stakeholders regarding socio-economic developments, challenges with human capital development (HCD) and policy responses to these challenges which fall within the remit of VET systems.

In view of the protracted duration of the COVID 19 pandemic, we felt that it is important to generate additional layers of evidence that capture developments after 2020, provide an insight into the changes in policy environments as a result of the public health crisis, and take note of perspectives from an even wider selection of stakeholders in each country. We, therefore, carried out two complementary rounds of evidence collection beyond the national reporting of countries.

The first of these supplementary sources were semi-structured interviews with country representatives who have direct exposure to, and stake in, the success of VET reforms (e.g. national and regional public officials). The interviews took place from December 2020 to January 2021 in an online setting and covered the target of system change reforms, experiences with implementation and translation into professional practice of these reforms, lifelong learning as a policy priority, and imagining the future.

The second source of supplementary evidence was a virtual focus group discussion with international partners in January 2021, which provided us with the most recent evidence. The focus group gathered 24 international experts and representatives of international organisations, such as the British council, GIZ, ILO, OECD, SDC and UNESCO, etc. to discuss along the same lines and themes as their national counterparts did in the course of the interview campaign. The focus group discussion was organised with the aim of gaining the perspective of the donors and matching it to that of the countries.

The interviews provided crucial updates about the influence of the pandemic on the shape and progress of policy reforms in VET and education more broadly, while the focus groups' discussion supplied an additional layer of insight into the priorities of the donor and

¹ The full report can be found at https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/torino_process_cross-country_digest_2018-21.pdf

international expert community regarding system change and anticipated developments and priorities for the future

The evidence from these three sources was compiled into a repository covering the immediate pre-pandemic period (2018-2020), the phase of initial lockdown and provider closures in 2020, and the time of emerging reopening and post-pandemic debate in 2020-2021 (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Cross-country evidence by source and time period

1.3 Method of Analysis

The findings presented in this chapter are the result of an inductive thematic analysis of 26 national Torino Process reports and 22 bilateral interviews with partner country representatives (Table 1), as well as a focus group with international partners, resulting in a total of 2 500 pages of reporting and transcripts, as well as big and administrative data for the period since 2011, which covered the VET sector and the socioeconomic context in which education and training take place.

The units of analysis were segments deemed to be of relevance because they referred – directly or indirectly – to system change in the area of VET which was a) intentional (purposeful) and b) ‘live’ at the moment of reporting, that is under implementation or planned for implementation.

After narrowing down the data to those of relevance in line with these two features, and after multiple rounds of inductive thematic analysis and negotiations of meaning, we developed a coding system which returned 5 000 segments of evidence that were deemed relevant for its explanatory power regarding three broader questions: 1) What are the system change priorities of countries participating in the Torino Process? 2) Why are countries engaging in system change along the lines of these priorities? 3) How are they implementing these reform priorities and what progress are they making?

Table 1

Sources of evidence: geographic coverage by type of source

	National report	Interview
Albania	x	x
Algeria	x	no
Armenia	x	x
Azerbaijan	x	x
Belarus	x	x
Bosnia and Herzegovina	x	x
Egypt	x	x
Georgia	x	x
Israel	x	x2
Jordan	x	no
Kazakhstan	x	x
Kosovo	x	x
Kyrgyz Republic	x	x
Lebanon	x	no
North Macedonia	x	x
Moldova	x	x
Montenegro	x	x
Morocco	x	x
Palestine	x	x
Russia	x	x
Serbia	x	x
Tajikistan	x	x
Tunisia	x	no
Turkey	x	no
Ukraine	x	x
Uzbekistan	x	x

At the next state, we disaggregated these broad questions into more specific inquiries which covered the relationship between reform priorities, including lifelong learning, e.g. whether some reforms tend to be conceived and implemented together with others; which of them lead to challenges and which to success; whether there is an association between reform targets and the likelihood of system-wide implementation; and also what role the international partners play in promoting system change.

This chapter presents a purposeful selection of findings from this rich repository of evidence, which reveal the relative significance of lifelong learning in the process of reform and system change in the partner countries at the time of evidence collection, the strategic significance of LLL as a driver of changes in policy and practice in VET, the interpretation of countries with regard to lifelong learning, as well as some of the more widespread challenges concerning the implementation of policy commitments in this respect.

1.4 Methodological Limitations

Our approach has advantages, such as flexibility of focus and stakeholder involvement, but it also has some important limitations.

The first one is that our findings remain interpretative in nature despite careful consideration and an ample degree of intercoder agreement. The positions, values and judgments of the research team inadvertently influence decisions about the coding which underpins the analysis presented in this contribution. While this can be also seen as an advantage because it provides flexibility and receptivity for different perspectives, the analysis may be susceptible to involuntary bias.

Another limitation is that the Torino Process reporting may vary to a considerable degree between countries in terms of stakeholder participation, the rigour of quality assurance, as well as the degree to which political sensitivities may have influenced the narrative around certain

themes and policy descriptions. The reliability and quality of evidence harvested from the national Torino Process reports may vary between countries, just like the information generated in the course of the interviews and focus group discussion. Therefore, the results of cross-country comparisons should be used with caution.

2 The Concept of “Lifelong Learning” in Our Research

As a growing number of learners and workers see their career choices and life prospects challenged by such developments, education systems will have to find ways of opening up and creating new pathways of learning throughout life – pathways which can accommodate the learning needs, circumstances and expectations of unprecedented diversity and number of learners. The cross-country evidence in the previous chapter suggests that this is an imperative especially for workers in sectors at risk who may need up- and reskilling, and for young people and adults more broadly to ensure that they remain employable in a new, digital, and green economy.

This paper cultivates a notion of lifelong learning that draws on this anticipatory, demand-driven perspective. It is aligned with an understanding of lifelong learning as a concept which puts people and their learning needs and settings at the centre of attention. In this sense, lifelong learning refers to any learning activity undertaken throughout life for personal, social and/or professional reasons, which may take place anywhere, anytime and for any purpose of importance to an individual (ETF, 2022)

Much of the evidence collected for this digest confirms that this may be an opportune moment for a structured reflection on how to best create and sustain viable learning opportunities for all who need and want them. At the time we carried our analysis in 2021 for example, the strategic plans for human capital development of most partner countries were about to renew or expire or were at the stage of long-term implementation planning (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Timing of national development strategies with reference to lifelong learning, ETF partner countries (2021)

Note. Countries marked with an * had a stand-alone lifelong learning/adult education strategy. Source: (ETF, 2022)

Overall, the Torino Process evidence shows that discussions on how long-standing challenges can be tackled by creating learning opportunities for much wider segments of the population than those usually covered through the formal education system are becoming

increasingly common and mainstream. Most countries thereby consider that the modification of policy and incentive frameworks and practices in education and training is the way to go in this respect (ETF, 2021).

3 Lifelong Learning as a Reform Target/Policy Solution

We opted for a broader, learner-centred understanding of lifelong learning because it reflects the heightened significance of the concept from the policy point of view in ETF partner countries. The concept presents LLL as a flexible, highly adaptable, and wide-reaching policy priority that can be mobilised as a narrative and course of action in response to a number of challenges, in particular challenges that can be traced back to the low or inadequate skills of diverse populations and to the changing skills demand in their environments, as discussed in the previous chapter above.

The broader concept of LLL has advantages also from the methodological point of view because it allows for more flexible interpretations at the stage of coding and analysis of evidence, which accounts for the diversity of contexts, formulations, aspirations and use-cases that the partner countries and stakeholders describe. In this sense, we translated the concept into a two-layered approach to the identification and recording of data of relevance to lifelong learning.

The first layer features segments with direct references to lifelong learning (Type 1 segments), such as that below:

Quote 1: *'Lifelong learning is also an important component of the National Employment Strategy (2017-2019). The political component of the said paper regarding strengthening of the education-employment relationship contains actions to encourage lifelong learning and to create open learning environments.'*

The second layer features segments which do not refer to lifelong learning directly (Type 2 segments), but which describe priorities and actions that fall in the field of lifelong learning in the sense of the definitions above, specifically the provision of opportunities for learning beyond formal education and in response to challenges that may be remedied through learning opportunities for populations that are not within the remit of the formal system. Quote 2 provides a typical example of a Type 2 segment:

Quote 2: *'(The) free education is intended for unemployed and self-employed youth, as well as people who do not have a professional education ... persons not admitted to educational institutions looking for work, from among those in difficult life situations and members of low-income families...'*

Despite our conceptual openness, it seems that for most partner countries it is rather early in the process of operationalising lifelong learning as a policy solution. In the vast majority of strategic plans which we reviewed, lifelong learning was not a stand-alone, clearly outlined strategic priority for development yet. Rather, most countries seem to still rely on decades-old legacy systems of adult education, referring to them as lifelong learning in the context of narratives about the preservation and perhaps optimisation of what is already available, and less so in the context of actual change. Quote 3 describes a typical example.²

Quote 3: *'Here we failed again, from my point of view. We don't offer lifelong learning, it's adult education that we offer ... But the programmes and everything, it's the same curriculum ... Of course, for lifelong learning, there are a lot of things that you have to change in programmes and curriculums, it's a different thing, but it depends on the needs of the candidates, whoever is interested.'* (Interview with senior official)

² The names of countries are omitted from the quotes on purpose to avoid creating an impression that the chapter singles out specific countries.

The snapshot we extracted from the stakeholder narratives and other data has showed us that, until 2021, none of the partner countries had reported lifelong learning as a solution (policy response) to external and internal challenges. This finding fits into the currently prevailing, broader pattern of limited strategic thinking about lifelong learning as a viable solution and a stand-alone area of policy planning.

However, there are important nuances. Experience from other countries shows that, among the many areas of policy and practice which countries may prioritise, some can be seen as the building blocks or elements of a lifelong learning (eco)system in the sense of an enabling environment for lifelong learning (London, 2011) (UNESCO, 2020). Further examples of such elements include adult learning strategies, qualification frameworks, outcomes-based qualifications, attention to key competences, validation of prior learning, training for jobseekers, better mechanisms for inclusive governance, closer cooperation among all those involved, etc.

Although, for the most part, the partner countries do not yet count lifelong learning as a stand-alone, viable policy area, they do devote time and resources to areas which are essential as elements of any lifelong learning system along the lines of the above. The Torino Process evidence too confirms that certain areas of policy response (the recognition of non-formal and informal learning in Quote 4 or career guidance in Quote 5, for example), are customarily seen as elements of broader, systemic efforts to provide learning opportunities for all in new and better, more accessible environments.

Quote 4: *'Until 2020, the project will develop assessment tools for the recognition of non-formal, and informal learning, determine the stages, procedures and methodology for the recognition of lifelong learning.'*

Quote 5: *'In order to promote the approach and participation of adults in lifelong learning, the Employment Agency carries out career guidance programs in vocational schools...'*

The selection of such elements in the 26 countries we covered is still small and includes the recognition of non-formal and informal learning, certain forms of provision of support and opportunities for (adult) learners and aspects of the partner countries' work on establishing and improving their national qualification frameworks (Figure 3).

The evidence also suggests that, as a consequence of the public health crisis, in 2020-2021 most of these areas – which were not among the most prominent to start with – have suffered a setback in terms of time, resources and attention as other policy areas with more imminent problems took precedence as part of the crisis responses of countries. The recognition of prior/informal and non-formal learning (RFIL) became even rarer as a point of reference, and while qualification frameworks remained relatively stable in the list of priority, support and opportunities for learners and adult learners in particular became considerably less present in the overview of key system change reforms provided by the partner countries. Overall, longer-term priorities have given way to more imminent tasks and challenges, such as support for staff, involvement of the private sector in addressing the fallout of the crisis, finding solutions for work-based learning and adapting the study and training content to the new reality.

An important conclusion to be drawn from the interviews is that lifelong learning is highly fragmented in terms of policy planning and action in all partner countries. The creation of opportunities for lifelong learning has not yet been consolidated as an area in its own right, with its own specific goals, solutions and responsibilities for planning and implementation. Perhaps it is understandable that in times that call for trade-offs, such as the pandemic, areas of relevance for lifelong learning are among the first to be 'downgraded' to make space for other priorities which are more 'mainstream' in terms of vision, planning and commitments.

Figure 3.

Areas of policy response in education and VET by aggregate prevalence, 2018-2020 and 2020-2021

Note. Source: (ETF, 2022)

For the partner countries, tackling this fragmentation may be an important step towards acknowledging lifelong learning as a high-priority, practical policy solution and not only as one aspirational goal among many others. Ultimately, the aim is to add lifelong learning to the field of viable, systemic policy interventions that are seen as pragmatic, sustainable responses to internal and external challenges.

4 Lifelong Learning as a Justification for Reforms in VET

4.1 Overview of Reform Justifications Before and During the COVID19 Pandemic

To document the prevalent justifications for reforms and to understand the relative significance of lifelong learning among them, we expanded our coding system to include the purposes of system change as reported by counterparts in ETF partner countries. Purpose in this sense refers to the reasons they give for the policy interventions presented in the preceding chapter. All sources had an abundance of segments conveying information about drivers of system change from the stakeholders' points of view and how these drivers relate to key values and aspirational goals in education and training, such as boosting access, improving efficiency, increasing the labour market relevance of learning and training outcomes, etc.

The creation of opportunities for lifelong learning may not be yet consolidated as a standalone area of policy action in the partner countries, but it is frequently quoted as a justification for actions in other areas. Our data shows that practitioners, decision-makers, and

stakeholders do refer to it when explaining what they aspire to and what they hope to achieve through various reforms.

In total, the analysis of data revealed seven more shared themes that describe the reform and system change aspirations of the partner countries: promotion of access and participation in VET; promotion of greening and lessening of environmental impact; better labour market relevance of VET outcomes; promotion of innovation and excellence; improvement of quality of education and training; increase in the efficiency of the provider network and its use of resources; and better working conditions for staff in the VET system (Table 2).

Table 2.

Reform and system change aspirations by prevalence, 2018-2020 and 2020-2021

Prevalence of justifications for reform 2018-2020			Prevalence of justifications for reform 2020-2021		
1	Labour market relevance	27.9%	1	Better quality	19.7%
2	Better quality	20.1%	2	Labour market relevance	17.7%
3	Better access and participation in VET	16.0%	3	Promotion and support for AE and LLL	17.2%
4	Promotion and support for AE and LLL	12.6%	4	System efficiency	16.7%
5	System efficiency	11.7%	5	Better access and participation in VET	15.8%
6	Promoting innovation and excellence	5.9%	6	Working conditions for staff	7.4%
7	Working conditions for staff	5.2%	7	Promoting innovation and excellence	5.4%
8	Greening and environmental impact	0.7%	8	Greening and environmental impact	0%

Note. Source: (ETF, 2022)

The evidence we collected suggests that before the pandemic, lifelong learning and adult education were not among the most common reasons for change. Strategic aspirations directly aligned with country commitments to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were the most prevalent reasons for reform: access and participation in VET; the quality of learning and training; and boosting the labour market relevance of VET programmes. Yet lifelong learning was more common than other, possibly higher anticipated and better established justifications, such as system efficiency, innovation, or the working conditions of staff.

During the public health crisis, the creation of opportunities for lifelong learning has become somewhat more prominent as a driver of change – an observation based on the frequent presence of narratives about the need to create opportunities for lifelong learning for learners outside formal education (see Quote 6, for example). In the period 2020-2021, LLL was the third most prevalent strategic target, while the quality of education and training became the most prominent concern.

Quote 6: *‘We have a lot of lifelong learning initiatives during this pandemic period. For example, people who lost their jobs were just insisting on training and so VET schools were organised, and the money was allocated for those courses from the government and from the ministry to retrain people for new occupations, to retrain adult education for particular skills, which are need in this changing world.’ (Interview with a civil society representative).*

It may be tempting to interpret this last finding as a testimony of strategic responsiveness in times of crisis, but, in reality, the changes we detected in the data for that period are in part also due to a more balanced, holistic approach to communicating about the reform agenda in countries. The COVID19 crisis forced many of them to reconsider and review their priorities and rearrange their resource planning and in the process of doing that, they recalled the justifications of all of their reform plans, including those that may have started a while ago.

4.2 Policy Solutions Which Promote Lifelong Learning

If lifelong learning is one of the more visible justifications for change, which of the policy responses we recorded in the previous chapter does it justify? In other words, which policy responses are supposed to create and promote opportunities for lifelong learning?

The evidence we collected shows that almost two-thirds of the countries which participated in the last round of the Torino Process have put in place reforms or have committed to reforms which, in one way or another, use lifelong learning as a justification or a long term aspiration: by promoting opportunities for lifelong learning in the form of second chance education, an expansion of the network of providers of adult education, upskilling and reskilling programmes and second chance education opportunities, etc.

Quote 7: *'Another priority is expanding participation in lifelong learning by increasing the number of adults included in second chance education, among others. (...) Certain groups, e.g. rural, people at poverty risk, ... have a low attainment level with no prospects of getting a job. (...) The main priorities for lifelong learning include the expansion of the supply of adult education ...; inclusion of the lower educated population (this is becoming a priority area of intervention ...); the development of an integrated system where learning can happen in different moments and in different forms, using the national qualification framework as a reference.'*

Quote 8: *'Starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, 147 vocational colleges and 143 technical schools will start implementing programmes based on the principle of 'Education throughout life'. Accordingly, the creation of a lifelong education system requires changes that will affect the scale, content and system of delivery of educational services.'*

All references of this type connect to one or more of the reform priority areas described in the previous chapter, although some policies are more readily associated with the creation of lifelong learning opportunities than others. The partner countries refer to lifelong learning most commonly as a justification for reforms that aim at improving support and opportunities for learners overall; boosting the inclusiveness of providers; and establishing viable mechanisms for the recognition of non-formal and informal learning – RFIL (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

Policy responses promoting lifelong learning, by prevalence in national reporting

Note. Source: (ETF, 2022)

Common to all is that, unlike some other areas of justification which address gaps and structural demands within the formal system, such as funding or infrastructure investment, lifelong learning remains the aspiration that is most closely associated with people and their individual needs. It drives change in areas which are meant to address these needs, such as inclusive education and support for additional learning opportunities, etc. So, although lifelong learning may not be a top priority for change, it is the only priority which systematically drives reforms that are meant to benefit learners directly.

Figure 4 shows that – except for RFIL, which is a more technical area – there is a degree of misalignment between what the previous chapter determined are policy areas/responses which count as elements of a lifelong learning system and what each country may consider to be the elements of such a system. One layer of divergence is the relative significance of policy areas in terms of mentions in reports and interviews. Here, the difference is most pronounced in the area of qualification frameworks, which are not as much at the focus of attention as they could or should be considering their role in promoting lifelong learning and in the area of inclusive education, which is much more prominent than anticipated.

There is another, deeper layer of misalignment at the level of substance and thematic scope. With regard to LLL, the declared connection between policy actions and the rationale for these actions is not always justifiable, despite statements to the opposite. For instance, in most segments which describe measures in support of opportunities for learners that are driven by an aspiration towards lifelong learning, the target is limited to initial VET and formal education more broadly.

Limitations such as this are substantial enough to bring into question the extent to which the link between policies and lifelong learning as the goal of these policies is clear and realistic enough. They also raise an important issue: there seems to be a discrepancy between expert interpretations of what lifelong learning is about (which are based on research and internationally communicated practice and experience) and the interpretations of countries, which are based on their own practice and local needs.

This diversity of interpretations also exists between and within countries, which suggests that, despite a widespread consensus about the significance of lifelong learning, no country has yet arrived at a comprehensive and convincing answer to the question of what a lifelong learning system means for them, and what its building blocks are. This is an issue that merits attention.

5 Conclusion

Our research findings suggest that the creation and promotion of opportunities for lifelong learning are starting an advance to the centre stage of the policy discussion in a number of countries – partners of the ETF, as many of them look for ways to address the learning needs of large and increasingly diverse populations and commence with the consolidation of long-term plans in this respect. The national Torino Process reports and the other evidence collected in preparation for this contribution show that lifelong learning is an area of aspiration for development which is most closely associated with people and their needs.

Still, LLL is an underdeveloped area of policy response. The narratives of countries are often dominated by referrals to decades-old legacy systems of adult education and preservation instead of change. Where they go beyond that to refer to LLL in a forward-looking manner, the link between policies and LLL as the broader goal of these policies and actions is rather weak, especially compared to other, longer-standing policy priorities.

Although ETF partner countries do not yet operationalise lifelong learning as a stand-alone area of planning and action, they do devote time and resources to other areas which are essential as the elements of building blocks of a lifelong learning system, such as recognition of prior learning or individualised support for learners. The selection of these elements is still quite

limited, and they are not necessarily well-connected and coordinated yet. This is part of a broader pattern of fragmentation of LLL as a policy domain, which may prevent the planning and coordination of actions and the viable division of responsibilities.

Addressing this fragmentation, for instance, through the development of dedicated strategies or policies, could be an important step towards acknowledging lifelong learning as a strategic yet practical policy solution and not only as one aspirational goal among many others. It is also important as a pre-condition for addressing the system dimension of skills and learning from a lifelong learning perspective. Overall, there is a need to work on accelerating the development of a coherent strategic vision for lifelong learning, which is in line with anticipated demand and country developments.

The “building blocks” approach to lifelong learning, which transpired in the course of the analysis, has some merits too. For those who wish to promote and support lifelong learning as a policy priority, each element of lifelong learning opens a possibility for engagement and action. Seeing lifelong learning as a selection of meaningful, interconnected policy areas can facilitate a well-informed, step-by-step approach to designing and supporting reforms in this domain (“one building block at a time”). The selection could connect to areas where countries are already working and engaging in system change instead of “importing” or imposing lifelong learning as one more policy commitment.

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Biographical notes

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